

EOSC POLICY BRIEF

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01
TOPIC: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-04 - Innovative and customizable services for EOSC
PROJECT: SciLake: Democratising and making sense out of heterogeneous scholarly content
PROJECT WEB SITE: <https://scilake.eu/>
GRANT NUMBER: 101058573
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SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

This policy brief enables EU-funded projects contributing to the advancement of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to report on progress and provide input for further policy analysis and development by the European Commission. This policy brief should be understood as complementary to the other mandatory reporting materials.

Policy background:

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a flagship EU initiative to deepen Open Science practices across the [European Research Area](#) (ERA). As such it contributes to several actions of the [ERA policy agenda](#) (in particular ERA action 1 & 8). EOSC is also recognised in the [European strategy for data](#) as the data space for science, research and innovation which shall be fully articulated with the other sectoral data spaces defined in the strategy.

Overall progress is steered by the EOSC tripartite governance involving the Union represented by the European Commission, the participating countries represented in the EOSC Steering Board and the research community represented by the EOSC Association. The second phase of development of EOSC (2021-2030) takes place in the context of the EOSC European co-programmed Partnership, which brings together the European Commission and the EOSC Association.

The [EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA) co-developed with the entire EOSC community sets 3 General Objectives (GO), 14 Operational Objectives (OO) and 14 Action Areas (AA).

General Objectives (GO):

1. Open science becomes the ‘new normal’, by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.
2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.
3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.

Operational Objectives (OO):

1. Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025;
2. Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023);
3. Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership;
4. Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership;
5. Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing);

6. Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership;
7. Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025;
8. Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership.
9. Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership.
10. Deploy and operate an authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024;
11. Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025;
12. Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025;
13. Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users;
14. Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023.

<u>Action Areas (AA) of a technical nature:</u>	<u>Action Areas (AA) related to boundary conditions:</u>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifiers 2. Metadata and ontologies 3. FAIR metrics and certification 4. Authentication / authorisation infrastructure 5. User environments 6. Resource provider environments 7. EOSC Interoperability Framework 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Rules of Participation 9. Landscape monitoring 10. Business models 11. Skills and training 12. Rewards and recognition 13. Communication 14. Widening to public and private sectors and going global

More information can be found from:

- https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/open-science-cloud>
- <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about>

A) Overview of contributions in relation to the EOSC policy and EOSC SRIA objectives

The following tables offer an overview of the contributions of SciLake to the EOSC policy and EOSC SRIA objectives.

Connection to General Objectives (GO):

GO1. Open science becomes the 'new normal', by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.

SciLake is a project that aims to contribute to the EOSC landscape, hence, naturally, its objectives are related to fostering and supporting Open Science in Europe. Additionally, openness is key to the success of the project in democratising and making more accessible the scientific knowledge. SciLake addresses the need to meaningfully connect diverse research outputs for specific domains. As Open Science practices have gained popularity, there has been a significant increase in the availability of scientific content, including not only publications but also datasets, protocols, methodologies, software, and workflows. SciLake is semantically linking these heterogeneous elements to create a rich, interconnected information ecosystem that supports the research community by accelerating scientific discovery and collaboration, enhancing understanding of the scientific landscape, and facilitating reproducibility and assessment of research. By offering this interconnected context to discipline-specific communities, SciLake plays a crucial role in advancing the broader goals of Open Science, contributing to a more transparent, accessible, and collaborative research environment.

Finally, SciLake advocates for open research information and contributes to development of open scientific infrastructures through its open source components. In line with this commitment, SciLake's activities are aligned with initiatives that are promoting similar principles, such as the Barcelona Declaration¹. SciLake partners are among the early signatories of this initiative and actively participate in its activities, further amplifying the relevant impact of the project.

GO2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.

SciLake aims to create an environment that streamlines the organization of scientific knowledge, enhancing the discovery of valuable literature, research products, and scientific facts, in general. To achieve this, SciLake is developing interoperability standards for Scientific Knowledge Graphs, which will be integrated across all SciLake components.

GO3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.

SciLake aims to deliver a prototype of an ecosystem designed based on a federated architecture (D1.2) that incorporates various components that focus on the better organisation of and easier access to scientific knowledge.

Connection to Operational Objectives (OO):

OO1. Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025;

¹ The Barcelona Declaration: <https://barcelona-declaration.org>

The work carried out in SciLake is closely aligned with various key areas related to the Minimum Viable EOSC. Notably, the focus on 'research data as a service' is particularly relevant, as SciLake aims to provide a Scientific Lake service that will expose domain knowledge through domain-specific Scientific Knowledge Graphs. Furthermore, SciLake partners are actively engaged in the EOSC Interoperability Framework, with particular interest in the 'service management and access framework' and the 'interoperability metadata framework.' These efforts are critical to the project's goal of delivering end-user services and enhancing interoperability between Scientific Knowledge Graphs, thereby facilitating their integration into value-added services. Finally, the EOSC area focused on 'monitoring, metrics, and accounting' is of particular interest, as the project aims to deliver a topic trend analysis component.

OO2. Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023);

Among others, SciLake will deliver a customizable topic trend analysis component, designed to perform tailored analysis of this kind.

OO3. Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership;

SciLake is expected to offer training materials and, in some cases, the technologies presented are helpful towards the wider adoption of Open Science.

OO4. Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership;

SciLake aims to contribute to the development of services, tools, and standards in scientific knowledge management, with a strong focus on Open Science. The project is designed to include a diverse set of pilots, each providing valuable feedback to refine and advance relevant standards and services. By adopting a co-development approach, SciLake aims to leverage insights from these pilots to shape and improve its offerings, ensuring they align with evolving needs and best practices

OO5. Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing);

SciLake is expected to offer services designed to provide insights the reproducibility and replication of research outputs, something that may be relevant to the particular objective.

OO6. Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership;

SciLake is expected to offer services designed to provide insights the reproducibility and replication of research outputs, something that may be relevant to the particular objective.

OO7. Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025;

SciLake is not directly related to this objective, however all software developed within the project is open source and open to the research community.

OO8. Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership;
SciLake is expected to offer services designed to provide insights into various aspects of scientific impact, as well as the reproducibility and replication of research outputs. These contributions can be useful for research assessment to incentivise FAIRness and open data practices in research.
OO9. Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership;
The EOSC Rules of Participation and the EOSC onboarding process are of interest for SciLake, because they can influence the rules of participation of resources to the SciLake ecosystem.
OO10. Deploy and operate an authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024;
While SciLake may exploit EOSC AAI service if needed, this objective is not directly relevant to the SciLake project.
OO11. Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025;
While SciLake is using PIDs for its purposes, this objective is not directly relevant to the SciLake project.
OO12. Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025;
This objective is not directly relevant to the SciLake project, however SciLake is putting effort into following relevant standards and making its resources (datasets, tools, services) discoverable in the EOSC landscape.
OO13. Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users;
SciLake is not directly related to this objective. However some of its components are offering insights on the impact of research products.
OO14. Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023;
SciLake will analyse the operational costs of its services and will investigate potential exploitation and sustainability pathways after the project completion.

Connection to Action Areas (AA):

AA1. Identifiers	While the SciLake services, components, and datasets make use of PIDs for various research-related entities (publications, authors, organizations, etc.) contributing to this area is out of the scope of the project.
AA2. Metadata and ontologies	The implementation of the SciLake ecosystem requires the development of standards for sharing scholarly metadata. SciLake will leverage well-established frameworks, such as the SKG-IF model , and extend them as needed to meet the specific requirements of the project. The results will be shared with relevant stakeholders, working groups, and EOSC-related projects and governance bodies to ensure broad alignment and impact.

AA3. FAIR metrics and certification	FAIR metrics and certification are not a primary focus of the SciLake project. However, FAIR indicators may be relevant to some degree in supporting the reproducibility assistance services offered by SciLake.
AA4. Authentication / authorisation infrastructure	While the SciLake services may take advantage of existing EOSC-related work for AAI if needed, contributing to this area is out of the scope of the project.
AA5. User environments	The SciLake ecosystem offers user environments tailored for different scientific domains. All resources will be discoverable in EOSC through the SciLake catalogue.
AA6. Resource provider environments	SciLake aims to establish a Scientific Lake ecosystem designed to enhance domain knowledge management by integrating open data (e.g., Scientific Knowledge Graphs), tools, and services from various project partners. All resources within this ecosystem will adhere to common interoperability standards, enabling seamless integration and bundling. Initially, contributions will come from project partners, but the ecosystem is designed to accommodate additional providers in the future, ensuring they follow the same interoperability principles.
AA7. EOSC Interoperability Framework	Enhancing interoperability among scientific knowledge graphs is in the focus of the project to facilitate the development of added-value services on top of those graphs. In that sense, SciLake is expected to contribute relevant insights and outputs that can be of interest to be considered in the EOSC Interoperability Framework.
AA8. Rules of Participation	Although SciLake will make use, where possible, of the principles related to the EOSC Rules of Participation, contributing to this area is not in the focus of our project.
AA9. Landscape monitoring	SciLake is not expected to focus on that subject.
AA10. Business models	SciLake will investigate potential exploitation and sustainability pathways after the completion of the project.
AA11. Skills and training	While SciLake is not specifically focused on contributing to this area, it does offer a variety of training activities on topics related to the project's technologies
AA12. Rewards and recognition	SciLake is contributing to the reform of the research assessment landscape affecting rewards and recognition. According to the EC report on Research Assessment ² , SciLake is expected to support Cluster 3 (“contributing to the infrastructure and dedicated tools and services for research assessment, including automated tools”) by developing data storage and AI-assisted analytic services built on customised takes on scientific merit, and AI-assisted services for automated assessment of reproducibility and replication and of scientific, societal or economic impact.
AA13. Communication	As an EOSC-related project, SciLake is always aligned with EOSC communication policies and contributes in the respective communication channels.
AA14. Widening to public and private sectors and going global	SciLake is not expected to focus on that subject. However, its datasets, services, and components can be used by public and private institutions.

² EC Report on Research Assessment: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/931335>

B) Key contributions subject to wider dissemination by the European Commission

Although the SciLake project is only halfway through its lifespan, various key contributions are already prepared for broader dissemination within the EOSC community. In the following paragraphs, we highlight the most significant of them.

Assessment. SciLake is expected to offer services designed to provide insights into various aspects of scientific impact, as well as the reproducibility and replication of research outputs. Early versions of these services have been released (more details in [D3.1](#) and [D4.1](#)).

Data. SciLake aims to provide a collection of domain-specific Scientific Knowledge Graphs that capture knowledge from various scientific disciplines. These graphs are datasets that can facilitate knowledge discovery and support a range of research-related activities and applications. Early versions of some of these graphs have been prepared.

Publications. All SciLake-related publications, which can be found in the [respective page of the SciLake website](#), are relevant.

Services. SciLake is building services to facilitate scientific knowledge management, knowledge discovery, and research reproducibility. Early versions of these services have been released.

Skills/training. SciLake's technology providing partners, with the support of OpenAIRE, have organised a series of internal webinars and have created, based on them, a series of open articles providing useful insights on various SciLake related technologies.

Software. SciLake is expected to deliver a suite of open-source components that can assist scientific knowledge discovery and research reproducibility. More details on the current versions of these components can be found in [D2.1](#), [D3.1](#), and [D4.1](#) of the project.

C) Synergies with other stakeholders

In the first 18 months of the project, SciLake partners actively participated in various EOSC-related events, including the EOSC Symposium and the EOSC Winter School. Additionally, SciLake is a member of the EOSC Association Working Group on Communication and Engagement for Horizon Europe projects. Through this working group, we ensure that SciLake plays a role in shaping strategies for community involvement and stakeholder engagement, contributing to the broader goals of EOSC. SciLake has also participated in two coordination meetings for EOSC-related Horizon Europe-funded projects, something that assisted the interaction with other project representatives.

Beyond these efforts, SciLake is actively involved in advancing interoperability standards for scientific knowledge graphs. To this end, several SciLake members are heavily engaged in the Research Data Alliance (RDA) working group responsible for developing the [SKG-IF](#) standard.

Furthermore, SciLake contributes to the European Commission's Open Science Policy and is at the heart of discussions surrounding the reform of the research assessment landscape, as referenced in relevant EC reports (see Section E for details). In April 2024, SciLake participated in a workshop organized by the European Commission (EC), aimed at aligning EC-funded projects with the EOSC Association Task Forces and CoARA in shaping the future vision and infrastructures for research assessment.

Additionally, SciLake organized a workshop on Open Science Knowledge Graphs at the Open Science FAIR 2023. This workshop featured several talks highlighting how Open Science Knowledge Graphs are revolutionizing the management, exploration, and analysis of scientific knowledge, with a particular focus on SciLake's technical advancements and pilot activities.

Finally, SciLake advocates for the importance of open research information and contributes to development of open scientific infrastructures through the open source components in its ecosystem. To this end, various SciLake members actively participate in activities around the [Barcelona Declaration](#) initiative.

D) EOSC challenges and lessons learnt of a policy nature

The current priority of the project, during this reporting period, is the development of SciLake datasets (e.g., Scientific Knowledge Graphs), tools, and services. Integration into the EOSC landscape is scheduled to start for a later phase in the project timeline, after M18 (June 2024). As a result, the immediate need for EOSC resources to address implementation challenges faced by SciLake partners has remained relatively low up to this point.

One key issue identified is the vast and complex nature of the EOSC-related project landscape, making collaboration with other projects not always straightforward. However, activities organized by EOSC-A, such as face-to-face meetings for EOSC-related projects and regular technical and communication calls, have significantly alleviated this challenge.

Additionally, navigating the complexities of the EOSC architecture and determining the best approach for integrating SciLake resources within this ecosystem present substantial challenges. These difficulties have been compounded by recent major changes in the EOSC architecture, further complicating the landscape. Nevertheless, several sessions held during EOSC events have provided valuable insights and resources to help address this critical need.

E) Link to other EU policy priorities (beyond EOSC)

In terms of EU sectoral policies, SciLake is poised to make contributions to the domain of "Research and Innovation" by advocating in favor of the adoption of Open Science practices and delivering technologies that can help enhance open research infrastructures. Moreover, the project is anticipated to offer valuable insights and resources pertinent to "Statistics" policies, including guidance on research-related measurements and access to essential tools, services, and data for analysis.

Additionally, while SciLake is not specifically focused on advancing any of the five EU Missions for Horizon Europe, its support for knowledge discovery in the pilot projects may have indirect impacts. For instance, it could contribute to the "Conquering Cancer: Mission Possible" through the cancer research pilot, as well as to "A Climate Resilient Europe," "Mission Starfish 2030," and "100 Climate-Neutral Cities by 2030" through the energy and transport research pilots. Additionally, SciLake's commitment to fostering and supporting Open Science inherently aids valuable research efforts in these fields.

Furthermore, SciLake also contributes to the European Commission's Open Science Policy and is placed in the core of the discussion for reforming the research assessment landscape. The *EC Report on Research Assessment* identifies four clusters of activities from Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects, including direct and indirect relevant contributions, from both planned and completed activities. According to the report, SciLake is expected to support Cluster 3 ("contributing to the infrastructure and dedicated tools and services for research assessment, including automated tools") by developing data storage and AI-assisted analytic services built on customised takes on scientific merit, and AI-assisted services for automated assessment of reproducibility and replication and of scientific, societal or economic impact. Finally, the EC Report also highlights relevant promising practices by the various projects, with SciLake being linked to "embedding and recognising Open Science practices", "catalysing and inspiring organisational change", "self-reflective approach to the development of recommendations and frameworks, for example through trialling or piloting", and "assessment of impact".

Finally, while SciLake does not focus on sustainable development goals, the project activities can be relevant to at least some of them. Indicatively, SciLake could contribute in the field of: (a) "Good Health and Well-Being" (Goal 3) as one of its pilots focuses on cancer research, and the SciLake ecosystem will support knowledge discovery in this domain, facilitating research advancements that could lead to improved health outcomes, (b) "Affordable and Clean Energy" (Goal 7) as one of its pilots focuses on energy research, and the SciLake ecosystem will support knowledge discovery in this domain, facilitating research advancements that could contribute to advancements in the domain, (c) "Industry, innovation, and infrastructure" (Goal 9) as the project is contributing to open research infrastructures, and (d) "Sustainable Cities and Communities" (Goal 11) as one of its pilots focuses on transport research, and the SciLake ecosystem will support knowledge discovery in this domain, facilitating research advancements that could contribute to advancements in the domain.

SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY (MAX 1P)

Not Applicable (this section should be filled only by projects in their final reporting period).

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